

EXPERIMENTAL OPTICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF TRANSPARENT MEDIA (PLANE GLASS, WATER-GLASS LAYERED STRUCTURE, AND CONVEX LENS) USING IMAGE-OBJECT SPATIAL CORRELATION TECHNIQUE

^{1*}Jayeoba Babatunde O., ²Mathew Timothy O., ³Olaifa Babatunde A., ³Adebajo Adelaja O. and ⁴Bolanle Yisau I.

^{1*, 2, 3, 4}Department of Science Laboratory Technology, Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro, Ogun State, Nigeria

²Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro, Ogun State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT: In-depth experimental observation of the resulting properties of light-matter interaction can pave the way for new applications in the evaluation of the suitability of materials for optical devices, such as lenses, waveguides, or coatings, and curriculum development. This study explores the nature of resulting images as a result of transmission and partial reflection of light with three major transparent media (plane glass (S_G), glass-water sandwiched (S_{GWG}) and convex lens (S_C)). The transparent medium sample is successively mounted on an adjustable optical bench where object/image distances are spatially varied to observe the nature of images formed with reference to the observer's position from the medium, d_o (20 cm). This procedure was repeated for the three samples of various object distances, U_m from the medium, U_m (5cm - 25cm) where the characteristics of the image formed were examined under longitudinal nature, magnification/size, and transverse orientation. The nature of an image formed from an object can be manipulated by altering the medium of transmission and object/image spatial displacement. The plane glass has the same characteristics (erect, same size, slight lateral displacement, and no lateral inversion) irrespective of the distance, whereas the convex lens demonstrated unconventional lateral inversion characteristics at some points beyond the focal point of the lens. With water sandwiched between two unsilvered plane glasses, the observed images are similar to that of a convex lens, except for the erectness in the longitudinal nature of the image with an inclusion of lateral inversion in both cases. This is attributed to the partial reflective characteristic of water that accompany transmission when sandwiched between plane glasses. Therefore, the heresy in optical illusion is a function of the distance between the medium and object, V_m . This new unconventional lateral inversion discovery beyond the focal length of the sample can be used as a decoy for security applications.

KEYWORDS: Optical illusion, transparent, longitudinal, transverse, lateral inversion, magnification.

1.0 Introduction

The interaction of light energy with matter is one of the most important observable phenomena. This field of study is termed optics in physics and has wide-spread applications in fundamental optics, material science, photonics, imaging systems, optical instrumentation, and engineering. Matters respond differently to electromagnetic waves, where this interaction causes multi-illusionary dimensions from the outside of a system (Dressel & Gruner, 2002). The perceptible observations resulting from the interactions depend on many factors such as: frame of reference or observation, the resulting properties of wave-particle (light and matter) interaction, the geometrical architecture of the incident ray, the nature of the incident ray, and the nature of the matter (system) (Jayeoba, Olaifa, Balogun, & Lawal, 2023). Everything is made observable within the visible spectrum through reflection because light energy has to shine on an object and the object has to reflect the incident ray from the object to an optical measuring tool (eyes); if light energy disappears, then there is no more observable dimension (Römer, 2005).

The interaction of light with matter has led to many applications in various fields of study, such as medicine, telecommunication, security, electronics, and energy. The propagation of electromagnetic waves through vacuum is a fundamental experience, an illustration of how the sun reaches us on earth. This combination of electric and magnetic forces, which vary in values, propagates perpendicularly to the direction of travel to interact with matter, where the interaction process can be manipulated to yield desired engineering applications (Kong & Ding, 2000). The system with which light interacts causes different behaviors and applications. These properties are essential in designing optical instruments, imaging systems, sensors, laser devices, and photonic applications, as evidenced by the works of Wu et al. (2023), Francis et al. (2023), Faluweki and Liang (2023), and Hu et al. (2024), who characterized different systems of material interaction with light using various experimental techniques, such as spectrophotometry, interferometry, optical coherence tomography (OCT), chromatic focal sensing, laser beam methods, and digital holography.

Electromagnetic waves are transverse and do not require a material medium for their propagation but can interact with matter based on Maxwell's equation (Born & Wolf, 1980). Many experiments have been conducted to study the optical behavior of some materials (Jiafa et al., 2022; Tagashira et al., 2024). The interaction of electromagnetic waves gives detailed characteristic properties such as refractive index, reflection, diffraction, interference, and polarization. Understanding the detailed characteristics of the resulting interaction is important for the application of any optical material, especially when using the image-object spatial correlation technique. This quantitative technique shows the quantitative relationship between an image distribution and its corresponding optical image after propagation through a transparent system and necessary three-dimensional transparent object reconstruction (Mathai et al., 2020). Thorough analysis of spatial correlations between input objects and transmitted or refracted images, extraction of refractive index distribution, optical distortion, focal behavior, scattering effects, and phase modulation

During the interaction of electromagnetic waves with matter, the signal could be absorbed, reflected, or transmitted, or any combination of these can occur. The summation of transmittance, reflectance, and absorbance is equal to unity for any material (Fedorov & Filippov, 1976).

Figure 1: Responses of Matter to Light

Applications of the interaction of light with matter, such as in microscopes used by medical research workers in their fight against disease; telescopes used by seamen and astronomers; and a variety of optical instruments that incorporate lenses, mirrors, or glass prisms, such as cameras, driving mirrors, and binoculars, all testify to the scientist's service to the community that require proper understanding of the propagation route of light passing through the medium (Jiafa, Weiguo, Yahong, Kejie, Hua, and Ronghua, 2023). Despite the advancement in optics, the accurate characterization of multilayer transparent systems remains difficult due to multiple reflections and interference effects. Characterization accuracy decreases in highly scattering or strongly refractive systems.

Optical characterization experiments aim to accurately determine these parameters under controlled laboratory conditions. Therefore, there is a need for experimental investigations of the image characteristics formed by common optical materials in the laboratory (plane glass, water-sandwich plane glass, and convex lens). This section will examine the phenomenal of transmission (refraction) and reflection.

2.0 Methodology

This section highlights the materials used for the experimental characterization of images formed by different optically transparent media and the experimental procedure used to generate images at different distances from the medium. The materials used for investigating the nature image seen through different media are as follows:

- **Adjustable optical bench with a medium holder:** The optical transparent medium and the object are mounted on this bench, which is graduated in centimeters for variation.
- **Object/image screen:** This is a white plate on which the objects are designed.
- **Markers:** Different colors of markers (Green, Black, and Red) are used for object representation in a vertical order.
- **Optically Transparent Medium:** The objects' images are observed and characterized through three optically transparent samples:
 - (a) **Plane glass:** Lateral shift observations in the direct measurement of refractive index make the plane glass a choice of system in this study.
 - (b) **Water sandwiched plane glass:** This system represents layered transparent media in which light propagates through interfaces with different refractive indices. The justification for the choice of this system is its applications in underwater imaging, biomedical optics, and temperature-dependent optical experiments.
 - (c) **Convex lens:** This modifies the propagated rays and image information, where the characterization parameters include: focal length determination, aberration analysis, modulation transfer function, and refractive index estimation.

The object in this study is designed by drawing three arrows of the same size and direction but different colors in vertical order on a white plane plate.

The medium of interest (transparent plane glass) is mounted on the optical bench between the observer and object.

For image characterization, the system/set-up is observed through the medium from a fixed reference point 20 cm from the medium.

Characteristics are observed and recorded for different media (transparent plane glass, water sandwiched glasses, and convex lens). The experimental setup is summarized diagrammatically in Figures 2a, 2b, and 2c for the three optical media.

Figure 2(a): Experimental observation through a plane glass medium.

Figure 2(b): Experimental observation through a glass medium sandwiched in water.

Figure 2(c): Experimental observation through the convex lens medium.

This procedure is repeated for the three samples in succession, where the position of the object from the medium is varied at U_o (2.00, 5.00, 10.00, 15.00, 20.00, 25.00, and 35.00 cm), where the characteristics of the image formed were examined and recorded under longitudinal nature, magnification/size, and transverse nature.

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1. Observed Image Characteristics with Plane Glass, S_G

Table 3.1: Observed Image Characteristics with Plane Glass at Different Object Distances, U_o (cm)

S / N	Image distance from the medium, V_m (cm)	Nature of the Image-Formed	Visual Setup
1.	5.00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Erect • Same size • No lateral inversion 	
2.	10.00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Erect • Same size • No lateral inversion 	
3.	15.00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Erect • Same size • No lateral inversion 	
4.	20.00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Erect • Same size • No lateral inversion 	
5.	25.00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Erect • Same size • No lateral inversion 	

The results in Table (3.1) show the image formed when light passes through the unsilvered plane glass sample, S_G . From the characteristics of the image formed, the refraction phenomenon dominates with partial or no reflection, where the presence of water introduces additional refractive interfaces and modifies the effective optical path. The transmitted image is virtual, erect, and of the same size (w.r.t. Object's position), no lateral inversion but slight lateral displacement (shift). The above characteristics explain why an object seen through a thick plane glass slab appears slightly shifted, it cannot be projected (virtual), same size depending on the object distance, and upright. The slight lateral displacement is due to the plane glass dominance's refractive property.

3.2 Observed Image Characteristics with Water Sandwiched Plane Glasses, S_{GWG}

Table 3.2: Observed Image Characteristics with Water-Sandwerved Plane Glasses at Different Object Distances, $U_o(\text{cm})$ ($m_o = 20\text{cm}$)

S / N	Object distance from the medium, U_o (cm)	Nature of the Image-Formed	Image
1.	≤ 5.00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Erect Magnified No lateral inversion 	
2.	10.00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Erect Magnified Laterally inverted 	
3.	15.00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Erect Magnified Laterally inverted 	
4.	20.00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Erect Same size Laterally inverted 	

5.	25.00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Erect • Diminished • Laterally inverted 	
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The results in Table (3.2) show the image formed when light interacts with the water-sandwich unsilvered plane glass sample, S_{GWG} . It can be observed from the characteristics of the formed image that there is a combined phenomenon of refraction and reflection. The final image has undergone major transmission-reflection-transmission in succession and therefore has position-dependent characteristics. The resultant effort of refraction and reflection does not affect only the longitudinal orientation as the image remains upright irrespective of object positions. Lateral inversion is set beyond 5 cm, which shows the dominance of the reflective property of the system, and the image magnitude begins beyond 20 cm.

3.3 Observed Image Characteristics with a Convex Lens

Table 3.3: Observed image characteristics with convex lens at different object distances, U_o (cm)

MEDIUM: CONVEX LENS

S / N	Object distance from the medium, U_o (cm)	Nature of the Image-Formed	Image
1.	5.00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Erect • Magnified • No lateral inversion • Object between F and OC. • virtual 	
2.	10.00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inverted • Magnified • Laterally inverted • Object between F and 2F. • Real 	
3.	12.00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inverted • Same size • Laterally inverted • Object at 2F. • Real 	

4.	20.00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inverted • Diminished • Laterally inverted • Object beyond 2F • Real 	
5.	25.00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inverted • Diminished • Laterally inverted • Object beyond 2F • Real 	

Table (3.3) shows the image formed when light interacts with the convex lens, S_C . It can be observed from the characteristics of the formed image that there is a combined phenomenon of refraction and reflection. The reflective property is zero or negligible below the 5 cm object position because there is no lateral inversion phenomenon. This is likened to a situation where the object is between the optical center and focal point of the lens, where the image is termed virtual.

Changes in the longitudinal orientation and lateral inversion characteristics simultaneously surfaced beyond 5 cm, and the decrement set in as the object distance was increased away from the optical center of the lens. A 12-cm object distance was deliberately examined to establish the focal point of the lens where the object and image sizes attain equality, as observed at the 2F of the lens. That is, the focal length is 6 cm

The strangest or unconventional characteristic demonstrated by sample, S_C , is the lateral inversion observed from 10 cm more than the object's position. This observation has never been recorded in the existing literature. This attribute shows that reflection surfaces beyond the object's position where the image is virtual and erect. This trade-off causes the appearance of lateral inversion.

3.4 Longitudinal Nature Characteristics

Examination of image characteristics at the same observer's distance (reference) from the medium, d_0 (20 cm), and the object distance from the medium, U_o (10 cm).

Table 3.4: Comparison of observed characteristics for different media

Observed Characteristics	Nature of the image formed with the plane glass, S_G	Nature of image formed with the water sandwiched plane glass, S_{GWG}	Nature of the image formed with the convex lens, G_c
Longitudinal Nature	Erect	Erect	Inverted
Magnification	Same size	Magnified	Magnified
Transverse Nature	No lateral inversion	Laterally inverted	Laterally inverted

4.0 Conclusions

Experimental characterization was carried out with the aid of an optical bench, where the nature of the images formed by three transparent media was observed and recorded. Three samples (plane glass (S_G), water sandwiched glasses (S_{GWG}), and convex lens (S_C)) were successively mounted with spatial variation of

object/medium at a fixed observer's position from the medium, 20cm, to study the longitudinal nature, magnification, and transverse nature of the image formed. The results show that irrespective of object's distance, U_o from the medium, the image is always erect, diminished and no lateral inversion was observed; an attribute that indicates the dominance property of transmission (refraction). The degree of image diminishing is inversely proportional to the magnification; therefore, this sample cannot be used to alter the perception of the object.

When the plane glass is filled with clean water, there is an alteration in the characteristics of the image observed in terms of magnification and transverse nature at the different object positions compared with the characteristics observed with the plane glass. The lateral inversion that occurs from a 10-cm object distance is attributed to the partial reflective ability of the water atoms sandwiched between the end-to-end orientations of the transmission of glass atoms.

The newly unconventional characteristic recorded during the experiment from the object's position beyond 10 cm is lateral inversion, while other conventional characteristics possessed by the convex lens still maintain their respective features.

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